

All Patient Cases (images and clinical data) collected until 24/04/2024 in the CHAIMELEON Repository related to Colon cancer.

ID: 2d87741d-77ba-45da-bdc1-71edc82ac557

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/2d87741d-77ba-45da-bdc1-71edc82ac557/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 838

Subjects count: 775

Age range: Between 33 years and 95 years

Sex: Male, Female, Unkown

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, COLOSCANNER, BRAIN, NECK, LUNG, WHOLEBODY, TAP, TORAX, COLOSCANNER EAU, THORAX, EXTREMITY, AORTA, UROSCANNER, THORAX / ABDOMEN, CAP, Unknown

Modality: CT, CR, DX